

Solvent Effects on the Kinetics and Mechanism of the Hydrolysis of Acetamide in Tert. Butanol-Water Mixtures

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Solvent effects on the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in various tert. butanol-water mixtures were studied in the temperature ranges 25° to 50°. In the acidic hydrolysis, the velocity constant decreased noticeably with successive addition of the organic solvent whereas the iso-composition activation energy increased in the same direction. In the alkaline hydrolysis, the velocity constant decreased noticeably on progressive addition of tert. butanol up to 30% by weight, then decreased slightly up to 40% and at last increased also slightly up to 50%. On the other hand, the isocomposition energy of activation increased slightly with increasing organic solvent content up to 40% by weight and then decreased. This trend as well as the isodielectric activation energies were discussed in terms of solvation effects. The calculated thermodynamic data and other parameters were discussed as evidences for the solvation effects and supporting the suggested mechanism. The reaction rate was correlated with solvent composition. Dielectric constant effect on the reaction rate was investigated on the basis of Elsemongy's equations. The refined $a\ddagger$ values (radius of the activated complex + radius of a water molecule) were calculated and found to be in the reasonable range 5.6-6.1Å°. However, these values account for the solvation of the activated complex and give an idea about the extent of solvation.

ACIDIC and basic amide hydrolysis has been studied recently and has been discussed in two reviews^{1,2}. In our laboratory, systematic studies of the acid and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide were carried out³ over a wide range of water-dioxane mixtures in order to clarify specific solvent effects on the reaction rate. The rate of acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide was measured⁴ in different iso-propanol-water mixtures. The calculated velocity constants, iso-composition and isodielectric energies of activation were discussed in terms of solvation effects and were confirmed by thermodynamic data. Structure, medium, and temperature dependence of acid-catalysed amide hydrolysis were discussed by Smith and Yates⁵. The kinetic acidity dependence and medium dependence of the activation parameters have been analysed. Alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in water containing methanol, glycol or glycerol was studied⁶. The effect per mole was more pronounced on ascending the polyalcohol series. The rate constants of the hydrolysis of protonated acetamide in dioxane-water mixtures were calculated⁷ from kinetic data and known acid constants of the amide. The acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of amides has also been studied in acetone-water⁸ and ethanol-water mixtures⁹. The rates were found to increase with increasing the dielectric constant. In the present investigation the solvent effects on the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in various *t*-butanol-water mixtures up to 75% by weight of the organic solvent are studied in the temperature range 25°-50°. The calculated thermodynamic data and other parameters are discussed as evidences supporting the suggested mechanism.

Experimental

Materials

Acetamide, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions were prepared as described before³. Pure tert. butanol of "Prolabo" quality was further purified by drying over anhydrous calcium sulphate. It was fractionated (b.p. 82.5°) after filtration from the desiccant. Boiled conductivity water was used throughout the experimental work.

Kinetic procedure

The rate of saponification was measured in the temperature range 25°-50° in pure water and water-tert. butanol mixtures up to 50% by weight. The rate of acidic hydrolysis was measured also in pure water in the temperature range 25°-50° and in water-tert. butanol mixtures up to 75% by weight in the temperature range 35°-50°. The rate of the reaction was followed by the methods mentioned before³. The infinity values in different tert. butanol-water mixtures were estimated to assure that the reaction is not of the reversible type. The values obtained were the same for the different solvent mixtures and assured complete hydrolysis. The hydrolysis of acetamide in acidic or basic media is a second-order reaction, and the bimolecular rate constant is calculated according to the equation,

$$k_2 = \frac{x}{a(a-x)t},$$

where a is the initial concentration of both acetamide and acid or alkali and x is the amount decomposed

at the time t . Calculation of the velocity constant k_2 was carried out by plotting $x/a-x$ against t in hours where straight lines passing through the origin were obtained. The slope of such lines (S) amounts to a k_2 , i.e.,

$$k_2 = S/a \text{ liter mole}^{-1} \text{ hr.}^{-1}.$$

Results and Discussion

Velocity constant and energy of activation

The results of hydrolysis in pure water and water-tert. butanol mixtures at 25°-50° are given in Tables 1 and 3. The plots of $x/a-x$ against t in hours gave straight lines passing through the origin. Typical plots at 25° and 40° for the alkaline and acidic hydrolysis respectively are shown in Figures 1 and 2. The second order velocity constants k_2 were calculated graphically and are included in Tables 1 and 3.

Fig. 1. Second order plots at 25° in *t*-butanol-water mixtures.

This system was found to obey the Arrhenius equation. The plots of $\log k_2$ against $1/T$, where T is the absolute temperature, gave good straight lines. From the slopes of these lines, the iso-composition energy of activation, E_a , were calculated and are recorded in Tables 1 and 3. In the case of acidic hydrolysis, it is evident from the results in Table 1

TABLE 1—VELOCITY CONSTANTS (IN LITER MOLE⁻¹ HR.⁻¹) AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ACIDIC *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt% M/l	0	10	20	40	56	75
$t = 25^\circ$	0.0371	—	—	—	—	—
$= 35^\circ$	0.1035	0.0825	0.0657	0.0550	0.0480	0.0381
$= 40^\circ$	0.1667	0.1358	0.1084	0.0944	0.0818	0.0668
$= 50^\circ$	0.4217	0.3387	0.2667	0.2438	0.2216	0.1819
E_a KCal/ mole	18.57	18.76	18.85	19.47	20.31	20.73

that k_2 decreases noticeably with successive addition of *t*-butanol. This trend is ascribed to the decrease of water concentration as well as to the lowering of the dielectric constant of the alcohol-water mixtures

Fig. 2. Second order plots at 40° in *t*-butanol water mixtures.

TABLE 2—ISODIELECTRIC ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION, E_a , IN ACIDIC *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Dielectric constant	10	25	40	55	70
E_a Kcal/mole	21.31	20.83	20.15	19.77	19.30

by progressive addition of *t*-butanol. On the other hand, the isocomposition energy of activation, E_c , increases with the successive addition of the alcohol. In the alkaline hydrolysis, it is seen that k_2 decreases noticeably on progressive addition of *t*-butanol up to 30% by weight, then decreases slightly up to 40% and at last increases also slightly up to 50%. Unfortunately, there is incomplete miscibility between water and *t*-butanol in alkaline solution containing more than 50% by weight of each and the kinetic behaviour could not be studied in these media. However, k_2 values for 30 and 50% *t*-butanol are nearly the same. On the other hand, E_c increases slightly with increasing organic solvent content up to 40% by weight and then decreases. The increase in E_c may be attributed to solvation of the activated complex to a lesser extent than the reactants.

The experimental activation energies involve a highly mixed dependence of the rate constant on temperature and of the dielectric constant of the medium. In order to obtain a more precise treatment of the results the temperature dependence of the dielectric constant should be eliminated. This is achieved by calculating the isodielectric activation energies, E_d , from the corresponding rate constants in isodielectric solutions. The latter were obtained by interpolation, at chosen values of D , from plots of $\log k_2$ against D . The values of E_d were then obtained from the Arrhenius plots, and hence the contribution due to solvation phenomena will be more or less minimised. The values of E_d for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis are given in Tables 2 and 4 respectively. However, it has been found that the isodielectric energy of activation is changing from 21.31

Fig. 3. Dependence of thermodynamic properties on the composition of the solvent at 35°.

TABLE 3—VELOCITY CONSTANTS (IN LITER MOLE⁻¹ HR.⁻¹) AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ALKALINE *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt%	0	10	20	30	40	50
M/l	0.000	1.314	2.600	3.811	4.972	6.063
$t = 25^\circ$	0.1361	0.1084	0.0872	0.0813	0.0785	0.0828
$= 35^\circ$	0.3103	0.2581	0.2053	0.1962	0.1885	0.1984
$= 40^\circ$	0.4681	0.3832	0.3119	0.2968	0.2874	0.2987
$= 50^\circ$	1.1176	0.8349	0.6714	0.6489	0.6345	0.6525
E_c Kcal/ mole	16.07	15.69	15.82	15.96	16.02	15.83

TABLE 4—ISODIELECTRIC ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION, E_d , IN ALKALINE *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Dielectric constant	80	75	70	65	60
E_d Kcal/mole	18.11	17.98	17.71	17.52	17.20

to 19.3 K cal/mole⁻¹ in the dielectric constant range of $D = 10-70$ in acidic hydrolysis and is changing from 17.20 to 18.11 K cal/mole⁻¹ in the range of $D = 60-80$.

Fig. 4. Dependence of thermodynamic properties on the composition of the solvent at 25°.

Thermodynamic data of the activated complex

Solvation effects could be understood from a study of the thermodynamic properties of the activated complex. These properties were calculated and listed in Tables 5 and 6 and are shown graphically in Figures 3 and 4 for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis respectively.

In the acidic hydrolysis, it is seen that ΔF^* increases gradually with *t*-butanol addition. According to the theory of absolute reaction rates, the increase in ΔF^* is a sign of solvation of the reacting species. This is in agreement with the increase of the energy of activation in the same direction. Therefore, solvation is expected to be more pronounced in presence of *t*-butanol. The heat content change, ΔH^* , increases successively by progressive addition of *t*-butanol. In the alkaline hydrolysis, the same is noticed up to an alcohol content of 40% by weight. In both cases, however, the variation of ΔS^* with composition is not linear. This nonlinear behaviour is a criterion of specific solvation in the opinion of Hudson and Saville¹⁰.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN ACIDIC *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES ΔF^* AND ΔH^* IN K.CAL./MOLE; $-\Delta S^*$ IN CAL./MOLE/DEGREE

Wt% <i>t</i> -butanol	0	10	20	40	56	75	
35°	ΔF^*	24.47	24.60	24.74	24.85	24.94	25.08
	ΔH^*	17.96	18.15	18.24	18.86	19.70	20.12
	$-\Delta S^*$	21.13	20.93	21.09	19.44	17.00	16.10
40°	ΔF^*	24.58	24.70	24.84	24.93	25.02	25.15
	ΔH^*	17.95	18.14	18.23	18.85	19.69	20.11
	$-\Delta S^*$	21.17	20.95	21.11	19.42	17.02	16.09
50°	ΔF^*	24.79	24.93	25.08	25.14	25.20	25.33
	ΔH^*	17.93	18.12	18.21	18.83	19.67	20.09
	$-\Delta S^*$	21.23	21.07	21.26	19.53	17.11	16.22

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN ALKALINE *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES. ΔF^* AND ΔH^* IN K.CAL./MOL; $-\Delta S^*$ IN CAL./MOLE/DEGREE

Wt% <i>t</i> -butanol	0	10	20	30	40	50	
25°	ΔF^*	23.49	23.62	23.75	23.80	23.82	23.78
	ΔH^*	15.48	15.10	15.23	15.36	15.43	15.24
	$-\Delta S^*$	26.87	28.58	28.58	28.31	28.14	28.64
35°	ΔF^*	23.79	23.91	24.05	24.07	24.10	24.05
	ΔH^*	15.46	15.08	15.21	15.34	15.41	15.22
	$-\Delta S^*$	27.03	28.65	28.69	28.33	28.20	28.65
40°	ΔF^*	23.93	24.06	24.19	24.22	24.24	24.21
	ΔH^*	15.45	15.07	15.20	15.33	15.40	15.21
	$-\Delta S^*$	27.08	28.71	28.71	28.39	28.23	28.74
50°	ΔF^*	24.16	24.35	24.49	24.51	24.52	24.51
	ΔH^*	15.43	15.05	15.18	15.31	15.38	15.19
	$-\Delta S^*$	27.02	28.78	28.81	28.47	28.28	28.84

Effect of water concentration

The variation of k_2 with water concentration was investigated by plotting $\log k_2$ versus $\log[H_2O]$ using Tables 7 and 8. In the acidic hydrolysis,

(Figure 5), two linear portions separated by a sharp boundary at a water concentration of 41.93 moles/liter (75.47%) were obtained. Above this water

Fig. 5. Variation of velocity constant with water concentration.

content the slope of the lines amounted to 2 while below this water content the slope amounted to a mean value of 0.33. This means that, in water-rich solvents, two water molecules are involved in the formation of the activated complex. However, at higher *t*-butanol contents, the number of water molecules decreased to 0.33. This result means that the internal structure of the medium suffered serious changes on addition of *t*-butanol to water.

In the alkaline hydrolysis, the plot of $\log k_2$ versus $\log [H_2O]$ gave straight lines having a mean positive slope of 2 in the water-rich mixtures, indicating the solvation of the activated complex by two water molecules. However, at higher organic solvent contents, the number of water molecules decreased gradually to a value of zero.

Effect of dielectric constant

The dielectric constants of *t*-butanol-water mixtures were obtained by interpolation from the data of Akerlof¹¹. The plot of $\log k_2$ versus D values given in Tables 7 and 8 gave straight lines of positive slopes as shown in Figure 6 in case of acidic hydrolysis, and gave straight lines of positive and negative

TABLE 7—VARIATION OF k_2 WITH DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND WATER CONCENTRATION IN THE ACIDIC HYDROLYSIS

Wt % log [H ₂ O]	0	10	20	40	56	75
	1.745	1.687	1.632	1.487	1.335	1.068
35°						
D	74.87	66.59	58.13	41.25	28.62	17.50
$2+\log k_2$	1.0149	0.9165	0.8176	0.7404	0.6812	0.5809
40°						
D	73.12	64.91	56.77	40.01	27.82	16.78
$2+\log k_2$	1.2219	1.1329	1.0351	0.9750	0.9128	0.8248
50°						
D	69.85	61.84	53.82	37.35	25.70	15.41
$2+\log k_2$	1.6250	1.5298	1.4260	1.3870	1.3456	1.2598

TABLE 8—VARIATION OF k_2 WITH DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND WATER CONCENTRATION IN THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS

Wt % log [H ₂ O]	0	10	20	30	40	50
	1.745	1.687	1.632	1.564	1.487	1.397
25°						
D	78.45	69.98	61.30	52.64	43.93	35.36
$2+\log k_2$	1.1338	1.0351	0.9405	0.9102	0.8947	0.9181
35°						
D	74.87	66.59	58.13	49.69	41.25	33.01
$2+\log k_2$	1.4918	1.4118	1.3124	1.2927	1.2754	1.2976
40°						
D	73.12	64.91	56.77	48.33	40.01	32.16
$2+\log k_2$	1.6703	1.5834	1.4940	1.4725	1.4585	1.4752
50°						
D	69.85	61.84	53.82	45.44	37.35	29.80
$2+\log k_2$	2.0481	1.9217	1.8270	1.8122	1.8024	1.8145

slopes in the water- and *t*-butanol-rich mixtures respectively. This behaviour is concordant with Elsemongy's equation¹² which predicts a linear dependence of $\log k_2$ on D . The refined values of $a_{\ddagger}$ (radius of the activated complex + constant) were obtained by using the same procedure mentioned before¹². These are given in Tables 9 and 10 for different *t*-butanol-water mixtures in acidic and alkaline hydrolysis respectively. The values of $a_{\ddagger}$ obtained are all within a reasonable range and change from 5.7 to 6.1 Å in the dielectric constant range of $D = 10-70$ for the acidic hydrolysis and from 5.6 to 5.8 Å in the range of $D = 60-80$ for the alkaline hydrolysis. It is evident from Tables 9 and 10 that the value of $a_{\ddagger}$ decreases on decreasing the water concentration, i.e., decreases by progressive addition of the organic solvent. This is in agreement with the fact that on progressive addition of the organic solvent, the structure of water would be destroyed progressively and the reacting species might become closer to each other and so the distance of closest approach $a_{\ddagger}$ would be decreased. However, these values account for the solvation of the

TABLE 9—REFINED VALUES OF $a_{\ddagger}$ FOR ACIDIC *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES IN Å

D	10	25	40	55	70
35	5.7	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.1
40	5.7	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.1
50	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.1

activated complex and give an idea about the extent of solvation. Considering the mechanism of the reaction (which is given below) the radius of the activated complex may be calculated where $a_{\ddagger}$ is equal to the radius of the activated complex plus the radius of a water molecule.

Proposed mechanism

In the light of the above considerations, mechanisms for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide should account satisfactorily for the role and the

TABLE 10—VALUES OF $\log k_2$ FOR ALKALINE *t*-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES IN Å

t° \ D	80	75	70	65	60
25	5.7	5.7	5.6	5.6	5.6
35	5.7	5.7	5.6	5.6	5.6
40	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.6	5.6
50	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.7	5.7

Fig. 6. Influence of dielectric constant on k_2 .

effects of the solvent on the reaction rate. It was noticed that successive addition of the organic solvent alters the rate without influencing the mechanism and so the mechanism is the same for the different solvent compositions. The analogies between the kinetic behaviour of acetamide in acidic and alkaline *t*-butanol-water mixtures and that acidic and alkaline dioxan.³ and isopropanol-water mixtures⁴ support our previous proposed mechanisms for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in dioxan-water mixtures³. Other evidences for these bimolecular mechanisms are the large negative values of the activation entropy ($-\Delta S^\ddagger = 16.10 - 28.84 \text{ cal. mole}^{-1} \text{ degree}^{-1}$) and the values of energy of activation ($E_c = 15.69 - 20.73 \text{ K-cal. mole}^{-1}$). These values are in excellent agreement with our previous proposed bimolecular mechanisms and support it.

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